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Accuracy of Dynamic Versus Kinematic Attitude Reconstitution

by L Lindegren

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1. Introduction

The attitude reconstitution (AR) uses SM transits and gyro signals (and possibly IDT data) to estimate the three attitude angles α_z , δ_z , ω as functions of time. In the simplest way, these angles result from integrating the kinematic equations, (A.3.4), which express their time derivatives $\dot{\alpha}_z$, $\dot{\delta}_z$, $\dot{\omega}$ in terms of the angular velocities in the telescope frame, $\underline{T}'\underline{\omega}$. The latter are obtained from the gyro signals, after scaling, drift correction, and projection onto the three axes. The SM observations are used to fix the integration constants (absolute attitude) and to estimate gyro drifts.

An AR according to these principles may be called kinematic (KAR) because it essentially relies on the kinematic equations. In particular, no dynamic assumptions are involved: the resulting attitude could for instance give angular accelerations which, if dynamically interpreted, would imply disturbing torques of an unrealistic magnitude. In contrast, a dynamic AR (DAR) incorporates dynamic modelling of the motion, which allows for unpredicted ("random") torques only of a certain magnitude (power spectrum) or compatible with model assumptions (harmonic or polynomial components).

Given the same input data (observations), the DAR is of course always superior in terms of resulting estimate variances (provided the dynamic model is realistic of course). The quantitative difference may be small, however, and is in any case not easy to assess. This note is an attempt to compare the two approaches by means of simple stochastic torque models.

2. The simplified problem

Although the actual dynamical equations, as well as the gyro and SM observation equations, can only be written by means of the full three axis attitude, it is sufficient here to consider a single axis (a) parallel to one of the SM slit groups. Let $u(t)$ denote the attitude about a relative to the nominal

attitude. We assume that a SM transit gives a direct measurement of $u(t)$ at the time of transit, with mean error σ_{SM} being the combination of star coordinate and timing uncertainties.

A gyro with input axis parallel to $\underline{a}$ will give a signal proportional to $\dot{u}(t) + \dot{g}(t)$, where $g(t)$ is the gyro drift angle. It appears that, in the frequency range of interest (~ 0.001 to 1 Hz), the gyro drift is fairly well modelled as a scaled Wiener process with incremental variance $r^2 dt$:

$$E[\{g(t_2) - g(t_1)\}^2] = r^2 |t_2 - t_1| \quad (1)$$

(cf. Appendix I). A realistic value is $r^2 = 0.001 \text{ as}^2/\text{s}$.

In reality there may not be a gyro with input axis along $\underline{a}$. However, a suitable linear combination of two or three actual gyro signals produces a "fictitious gyro" signal referring to $\underline{a}$ and with roughly the same noise properties as that of a real gyro. Thus, by choosing $\underline{a}$ parallel to the SM slits and to the fictitious gyro input axis, the observation equations do not involve the attitude angles about the axes normal to $\underline{a}$. Turning now to the dynamical (Euler) equations, we can also here isolate the motion about $\underline{a}$ from those of the other axes by regarding the various cross-couplings as perturbing torques which are, to the largest part, predictable. Amplitudes of unpredictable cross-coupling torques can be assessed and go into the stochastic torque model:

The total unpredictable torque $e(t)$, due to solar radiation pressure, gyros, thruster-induced vibrations, and nutation phenomena, is modelled as a stationary stochastic process with known rational power spectral density $P_e(f)$. We shall in particular study a white-noise spectrum ($P_e = \text{const}$) analytically, while more general spectra may be treated by numerical methods.

With the above assumptions and simplifications, our problem is the following. Consider the optimum estimation of $u(t)$ by KAR and DAR. In both cases the same observations are used, namely a continuous gyro signal $\dot{u} + \dot{g}$ with noise according to (1), and an infinite sequence of equidistant SM transits (at $t = nT$), each providing an independent estimate of $u(nT)$ with mean error σ_{SM} . The time-averaged variance of the u -estimate is required for the two cases.

3. Kinematic reconstitution

3.1. Filtered estimate

The filtered estimate $\hat{u}(t)$ is based on data up to and including time t . Let $p(t)$ be the variance of $\hat{u}(t)$. At the SM transits ($t = nT$, $n = \text{integer}$), there are discontinuities in that $p(t)$ drops from $p(nT^-)$ immediately before the transit to $p(nT^+)$ immediately after. We have, by adding statistical weights,

$$p(nT^+)^{-1} = p(nT^-)^{-1} + \sigma_{SM}^{-2} \quad (2)$$

In the interval $nT < t < (n+1)T$ between transits, $p(t)$ increases due to accumulated gyro noise. Since $E[g(t) - g(nT)] = 0$, from the properties of the Wiener process, the filtered estimate for $nT < t < (n+1)T$ is simply

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{u}(t) &= \hat{u}(nT) + \int_{nT}^t [\dot{u}(t) + \dot{g}(t)] dt = \\ &= \hat{u}(nT) + [u(t) - u(nT)] + [g(t) - g(nT)] \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Since $g(t) - g(nT)$ is moreover independent of the history of g before nT , and therefore also independent of $\hat{u}(nT)$, we get from (1)

$$p(t) = p(nT^+) + r^2(t - nT), \quad nT < t < (n+1)T \quad (4)$$

In particular,

$$p[(n+1)T^-] = p(nT^+) + r^2T \quad (5)$$

Independent of the initial conditions, a steady-state situation eventually develops, in which the loss of information between transits, due to the gyro drift, is exactly balanced by the information gain on a transit. Then

$$p[(n+1)T^-] = p(nT^-) \quad (6)$$

and $p(t)$ becomes a regular saw-tooth function with period T (Fig. 1a). With $p_{\max} := p(nT^-)$ and $p_{\min} := p(nT^+)$ we have from (2) and (5)

$$\frac{1}{p_{\min}} = \frac{1}{p_{\max}} + \frac{1}{\sigma_{SM}^2}, \quad p_{\max} = p_{\min} + r^2T \quad (7)$$

FIGURE 1a-c. Steady-state evolution of the variance of the filtered estimate (p), back-filtered estimate ($\hat{p}$), and smoothed estimate (p^*).

with solution

$$p_{\min} = -\frac{1}{2}r^2T + \left[\left(\frac{1}{2}r^2T\right)^2 + \sigma_{SM}^2 r^2 T \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (8a)$$

$$p_{\max} = \frac{1}{2}r^2T + \left[\left(\frac{1}{2}r^2T\right)^2 + \sigma_{SM}^2 r^2 T \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (8b)$$

If we define the average filter variance $\bar{p}$ as the geometric mean between $p_{\min}$ and $p_{\max}$, we have simply

$$\bar{p} = \sigma_{SM} r^2 T^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (9)$$

That is, the average filter variance is the geometric mean of the transit variance (σ_{SM}^2) and the gyro drift angle variance between transits (r^2T).

3.2. Smoothed estimate

For the on-ground AR we have access also to "future" observations when estimating $u(t)$. The smoothed estimate $u^*(t)$ is the weighted mean of the filtered estimate $\hat{u}(t)$ based on data $\leq t$, and the backward-filtered estimate $\overleftarrow{u}(t)$ based on data $> t$. The variance of the smoothed estimate is clearly

$$p^*(t) = \left[p(t)^{-1} + \overleftarrow{p}(t)^{-1} \right]^{-1} \quad (10)$$

$\overleftarrow{p}(t)$, the variance of the backward-filter estimate, is the same saw-tooth function as $p(t)$, only with reversed time axis (Fig. 1b). Thus, in the interval $nT \leq t \leq (n+1)T$,

$$\begin{aligned} p^*(nT+\tau) &= \left[(p_{\min} + r^2\tau)^{-1} + (p_{\max} - r^2\tau)^{-1} \right]^{-1} = \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\sigma_{SM}^2 r^2 T + r^4 \tau(T-\tau) \right] \left[\left(\frac{1}{2}r^2T\right)^2 + \sigma_{SM}^2 r^2 T \right]^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (0 \leq \tau \leq T) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

(Fig. 1c). The minimum smoothed variance occurs at $\tau = 0$ or T , viz.

$$p_{\min}^* = \frac{1}{2} \left[\sigma_{SM}^2 r^2 T \right] \left[\left(\frac{1}{2}r^2T\right)^2 + \sigma_{SM}^2 r^2 T \right]^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (12)$$

while the maximum, at $\tau = \frac{1}{2}T$, is

$$p_{\max}^* = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{1}{2}r^2T\right)^2 + \sigma_{SM}^2 r^2 T \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (13)$$

If we again define the average variance as the geometric mean between the two extreme values, we have

$$\bar{p}^* = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{SM} r T^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (14)$$

Thus, the average smoothed variance is exactly half the average filtered variance:

$$\bar{p}^* = \frac{1}{2} \bar{p} \quad (15)$$

This result is of course very natural in that the smoothed estimate is based on twice as many observations (within a certain time distance) as the filtered estimate. Since filtering is much easier to analyse, we shall assume that (15) holds also for more sophisticated methods of AR, such as DAR. We thus consider only the filtering problem below.

4. Dynamic reconstitution

4.1. General numeric method

For a wide class of rational power spectral densities $P_e(f)$, the random torque $e(t)$ can be represented by

$$e(t) = \underline{b}' \underline{x} \quad (16)$$

$$d\underline{x} = \underline{\Phi} \underline{x} dt + \underline{\Gamma} d\underline{w}'' \quad (17)$$

(Appendix I), where $\underline{x}(t)$ is a stochastic vector of the same order (k) as the polynomial in f^2 in the denominator of $P_e(f)$. (The case of white torque noise, $k = 0$, is treated separately below.) We can now construct a state vector $\underline{s}(t)$ of dimension $n = k + 2$, the first two elements of which are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} s_1(t) &:= u(t) \\ s_2(t) &:= \dot{u}(t) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (18)$$

The remaining elements are whatever variables needed to incorporate (16) - (17). The resulting dynamical model can be put on the form

$$d\underline{s} = \underline{F}\underline{s} dt + \underline{G}d\underline{w} \quad (19)$$

with matrices of dimension $\underline{F}(n,n)$ and $\underline{G}(n,n)$ and a unit Wiener process vector $\underline{w}(t)$ of length n . The gyro signal $\underline{z}(t)$ is a 1-dimensional vector represented by the observation equation

$$d\underline{z} = \underline{A}\underline{s} dt + \underline{R}d\underline{w} \quad (20)$$

with

$$\underline{A} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & \underbrace{0 \dots 0}_{n-2 \text{ zeroes}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \underline{R} = (r), \quad \underline{w} = (w(t)) \quad (21)$$

The covariance of the filtered estimate $\hat{\underline{s}}(t)$ is called $\underline{P}(t)$. Between SM transits, its time evolution is governed by the Riccati equation (Appendix II)

$$\dot{\underline{P}} = \underline{F}\underline{P} + \underline{P}\underline{F}' + \underline{G}\underline{G}' - \underline{P}\underline{A}'(\underline{R}\underline{R}')^{-1}\underline{A}\underline{P} \quad (22)$$

The evolution from $t = nT+$ to $(n+1)T-$ can be obtained in the form

$$\underline{P}[(n+1)T-] = \left[\underline{L}_{21} + \underline{L}_{22}\underline{P}(nT+) \right] \left[\underline{L}_{11} + \underline{L}_{12}\underline{P}(nT+) \right]^{-1} \quad (23)$$

with

$$\begin{pmatrix} \underline{L}_{11} & \underline{L}_{12} \\ \underline{L}_{21} & \underline{L}_{22} \end{pmatrix} = \exp \left[T \begin{pmatrix} -\underline{F}' & \underline{A}'(\underline{R}\underline{R}')^{-1}\underline{A} \\ \underline{G}\underline{G}' & \underline{F} \end{pmatrix} \right] \quad (24)$$

At a transit ($t = nT$), the covariance is updated according to

$$\underline{P}(nT+)^{-1} = \underline{P}(nT-)^{-1} + \underline{W} \quad (25)$$

where $\underline{W}$ is an (n,n) -matrix $\text{diag}[\sigma_{SM}^{-2} \ 0 \ 0 \ \dots \ 0]$.

In the steady state, $\underline{P}[(n+1)T-] = \underline{P}(nT-)$ and we have to solve the two simultaneous equations (23) and (25). It is possible to do this directly by eliminating either $\underline{P}(nT-)$ or $\underline{P}(nT+)$; the resulting equation has the form of a steady-state Riccati equation and can be solved by the eigenvalue-

-eigenvector method described in Appendix II, eqns (II.11) - (II.12). It is however simpler just to iterate between (22) and (25), starting with $\underline{p}(nT^+) = \underline{0}$. This usually converges in 10 - 20 steps and is a numerically very stable procedure. Computing the exponential in (24) may on the other hand present numerical problems and double precision must be used.

Having solved $\underline{p}_{\min} = \underline{p}(nT^+)$ and $\underline{p}_{\max} = \underline{p}(nT^-)$ we then take the geometric mean, divided by 2, as the average smoothed variance,

$$\bar{p}_{\text{DAR}}^* = \frac{1}{2} [(p_{11})_{\min} (p_{11})_{\max}]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (26)$$

in order to compare with p_{KAR}^* computed by (14).

For greater clarity, we give below the dynamical models (F and G) for three simple torque spectra.

Case 1: White noise spectrum

The torque $e(t)$ is modelled as white noise,

$$e(t) = v \dot{w}(t) \quad (27)$$

where $w(t)$ is a unit Wiener process (Appendix I). The power spectral density (PSD) is

$$P_e(f) = 2v^2 \quad (28)$$

If J is the moment of inertia about the $\underline{a}$ axis, we have the equation of motion

$$\ddot{u}(t) = J^{-1} e(t) \quad (29)$$

or, in differential form,

$$d\dot{u} = (v/J) dw \quad (30)$$

With the state vector ($n = 2$)

$$\underline{s}(t) = \begin{pmatrix} u(t) \\ \dot{u}(t) \end{pmatrix} \quad (31)$$

the process equations become

$$\left. \begin{aligned} du &= \dot{u} dt \\ d\dot{u} &= (v/J) d\dot{w} \end{aligned} \right\} \Leftrightarrow d\underline{s} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \underline{s} dt + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & v/J \end{pmatrix} d\underline{w} \quad (32)$$

which defines $\underline{F}$ and $\underline{G}$ in (19).

Case 2: Markov spectrum

Band-limited white noise with cut-off frequency f_0 (Fig. 2),

$$P_e(f) = 2v^2/[1 + (f/f_0)^2] \quad (33)$$

is generated by the first-order differential equation

$$\dot{e} + a_0 e = b_0 \dot{w} \quad (34)$$

with

$$a_0 = 2\pi f_0, \quad b_0 = 2\pi f_0 v \quad (35a, b)$$

The total power (torque variance) is

$$\sigma_e^2 = \int_0^{\infty} P_e(f) df = \frac{1}{2} b_0^2 / a_0 = \pi f_0 v^2 \quad (36)$$

By means of (29) we write (34) in the differential form

$$d\ddot{u} = -a_0 \ddot{u} dt + (b_0/J) d\dot{w} \quad (37)$$

With the state vector ($n = 3$)

$$\underline{s}(t) = \begin{pmatrix} u(t) \\ \dot{u}(t) \\ \ddot{u}(t) \end{pmatrix} \quad (38)$$

we finally obtain

$$d\underline{s} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -a_0 \end{pmatrix} \underline{s} dt + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & b_0/J \end{pmatrix} d\underline{w} \quad (39)$$

defining $\underline{F}$ and $\underline{G}$.

Case 3: Damped-oscillator spectrum

If the stochastic process $e(t)$ satisfies a second-order differential equation driven by white noise,

$$\ddot{e} + a_1 \dot{e} + a_0 e = b_0 \dot{w} \quad (40)$$

we have the PSD

$$P_e(f) = \frac{2b_0^2}{(\omega^2 - a_0)^2 + a_1^2 \omega^2}, \quad \omega = 2\pi f \quad (41)$$

with variance

$$\sigma_e^2 = \int_0^{\infty} P_e(f) df = b_0^2 / (2a_0 a_1) \quad (42)$$

The shape of the PSD depends on the damping parameter $\zeta = a_1 / (2a_0)$, Figure 3. For $\zeta < 1$ there is a resonance peak near $f_0 = a_0^{1/2} / (2\pi)$, with FWHM $\sim (2\zeta)^{1/2} f_0$ and comprising a fraction $\sim 1 - \zeta$ of the total power. For $\zeta = 1$ the PSD is a good approximation of band-limited white noise with $P_e \approx 2b_0^2 / a_0^2$ for $f < f_0$ and steeply decreasing power ($\propto f^{-4}$) for $f > f_0$. [Cf. the Markov spectrum, (33) and Fig. 2, which goes as f^{-2} above the cut-off frequency.] For $\zeta > 1$ there is an intermediate region roughly from $\zeta^{-1/2} f_0$ to $\zeta^{1/2} f_0$ where the power decreases as f^{-2} .

From (29) and (40) we get

$$d\ddot{u} = -a_0 \ddot{u} dt - a_1 \dot{\ddot{u}} dt + (b_0/J) dw \quad (43)$$

With state vector ($n = 4$)

$$\underline{s} = \left(u(t) \quad \dot{u}(t) \quad \ddot{u}(t) \quad \dot{\ddot{u}}(t) \right)' \quad (44)$$

we then have the process equation

$$d\underline{s} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -a_0 & -a_1 \end{pmatrix} \underline{s} dt + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & b_0/J \end{pmatrix} d\underline{w} \quad (45)$$

FIGURE 3. Damped-oscillator spectrum

$$P(f) = P(0) / [\{ (f/f_0)^2 - 1 \}^2 + 2\zeta(f/f_0)^2]$$

FIGURE 2. Markov spectrum $P(f) = P(0) / [1 + (f/f_0)^2]$

4.2. Analytical approximation

The DAR covariance is obtained by combining the Riccati equation (22) for the intervals between transits with the SM update equation (25). An approximate solution can be found by introducing the latter equation into the Riccati equation and computing the steady-state solution by the eigenvalue-eigenvector method of Appendix II. This is done by rewriting (25) as

$$\underline{P}(-) - \underline{P}(+) = \underline{P}(-)\underline{W}\underline{P}(+) \quad (46)$$

and replace it with the approximation

$$T \dot{\underline{P}} = \bar{\underline{P}}\underline{W}\bar{\underline{P}} \quad (47)$$

Here, we have neglected $\ddot{\underline{P}}$ on the left side and substituted some average covariance $\bar{\underline{P}}$ for $\underline{P}(-)$ and $\underline{P}(+)$ on the right side. Combined with (22), where we similarly put $\underline{P} = \bar{\underline{P}}$, we get

$$\underline{0} = \underline{F}\bar{\underline{P}} + \bar{\underline{P}}\underline{F}' + \underline{G}\underline{G}' - \bar{\underline{P}}\underline{S}\bar{\underline{P}} \quad (48)$$

where

$$\underline{S} := \underline{A}'(\underline{R}\underline{R}')^{-1}\underline{A} + \frac{1}{T}\underline{W} = \text{diag} \left(1/(\underline{T}\sigma_{SM}^2) \quad r^{-2} \quad 0 \quad \dots \quad 0 \right) \quad (49)$$

obviously represents the weight per unit time of the gyro plus SM observations. Eqn (48) can be regarded as a steady-state Riccati equation for $\bar{\underline{P}}$ ($\dot{\bar{\underline{P}}} = \underline{0}$) which may be solved according to (II.11) - (II.12) with $\underline{S}$ replacing $\underline{A}'(\underline{R}\underline{R}')^{-1}\underline{A}$ in the Hamiltonian (II.6). We shall do the exercise for

Case 1: White noise spectrum

The Hamiltonian for $n = 2$ and $\underline{F}$, $\underline{G}$ according to (32),

$$\underline{H} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & T^{-1}\sigma_{SM}^{-2} & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & r^{-2} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & v^2/J^2 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (50)$$

has the eigenvalues

$$\lambda = \pm(v/2Jr) \left[(1+\xi)^{\frac{1}{2}} \pm (1-\xi)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] \quad (51)$$

(for the four sign combinations), where

$$\xi := 2Jr^2/(vT^{\frac{1}{2}}\sigma_{SM}) \quad (52)$$

Corresponding eigenvectors are for instance

$$\underline{h} = (T^{-1}\sigma_{SM}^{-2} \quad \lambda^3 J^2/v^2 \quad \lambda \quad \lambda^2)' \quad (53)$$

If λ_1, λ_2 are the two eigenvalues with positive real parts, we have from (II.11)

$$\underline{D}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} T^{-1}\sigma_{SM}^{-2} & T^{-1}\sigma_{SM}^{-2} \\ \lambda_1^3 J^2/v^2 & \lambda_2^3 J^2/v^2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \underline{D}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_1 & \lambda_2 \\ \lambda_1^2 & \lambda_2^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (54)$$

Extracting the upper-left element of $\bar{P} = \underline{D}_2 \underline{D}_1^{-1}$, we get the average variance of $\hat{u}(t)$,

$$\bar{p}_{11} = T\sigma_{SM}^2 \lambda_1 \lambda_2 (\lambda_1 + \lambda_2) (\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_1 \lambda_2 + \lambda_2^2)^{-1} = \quad (55)$$

$$= \sigma_{SM} r T^{\frac{1}{2}} (1+\xi)^{\frac{1}{2}} (1+\frac{1}{2}\xi)^{-1} \quad (55)$$

Comparing with Section 3 we obtain

$$\bar{p}_{DAR}^* = \bar{p}_{KAR}^* (1+\xi)^{\frac{1}{2}} (1+\frac{1}{2}\xi)^{-1} \quad (56)$$

In case of strong perturbations (large v) or low gyro drift (small r), $\xi \rightarrow 0$ and $\bar{p}_{DAR}^* \rightarrow \bar{p}_{KAR}^*$ as expected. In the opposite limit of low torque noise, $\xi \gg 1$ and (56) becomes

$$\bar{p}_{DAR}^* \approx (v/2J)^{\frac{1}{2}} (T\sigma_{SM}^2)^{3/4} \quad (57)$$

This is independent of r , showing that the gyro in this case no longer contributes to the AR.

The ratio of dynamic to kinematic variance, $(1+\xi)^{\frac{1}{2}}(1+\frac{1}{2}\xi)^{-1}$, is shown in Table 1. It is seen that DAR is significantly better only if $\xi \gtrsim 3$.

Table 1. Ratio of dynamic to kinematic variance, $\bar{p}_{\text{DAR}}^*/\bar{p}_{\text{KAR}}^*$, as function of $\xi = 2Jr^2/(v\sigma_{\text{SM}}T^{\frac{1}{2}})$

ξ	10^{-2}	0.1	1	3	10	30	10^2	10^3	10^4
DAR/KAR	1.0000	.9989	.9428	.8000	.5528	.3480	.1971	.0632	.0200

5. Results

5.1. Kinematic reconstitution

The real-time AR uses kinematic filtering to which (9) applies. The mean time between transits of SM stars (1.4 deg^{-2}) at a single slit group (transverse width = 20 am) is $T = 43 \text{ s}$. With $\sigma_{\text{SM}} = 1.1 \text{ as}$ and $r^2 = 0.001 \text{ as}^2/\text{s}$ we find

$$\sigma_{\text{RTAD}} = \bar{p}_{\text{KAR}}^{\frac{1}{2}} = 0.48 \text{ as} \quad (58)$$

in fair agreement with MATRA's $\sigma_{\phi} = 0.71 \text{ as}$, $\sigma_{\theta} = 0.50 \text{ as}$, $\sigma_{\psi} = 0.45 \text{ as}$ (E22-HIP-03225, p. 503).

For the on-ground AR, after the positions have been updated, we may take $\sigma_{\text{SM}} = 0.08 \text{ as}$ for the SM stars, $T = 43 \text{ s}$, $r^2 = 0.001 \text{ as}^2/\text{s}$, and use eqn (14):

$$\sigma_{\text{OGAR}} = (\bar{p}_{\text{KAR}}^*)^{\frac{1}{2}} = 0.091 \text{ as} \quad (59)$$

to be compared with MATRA's $\sigma_{\phi} = 0.15 \text{ as}$, $\sigma_{\theta} = 0.10 \text{ as}$ (E22-HIP-03225, p. 512, estimated from diagrams).

Of the greatest interest is the accuracy of the on-ground AR using only IC positions. The quality of these is very heterogeneous, but we can still estimate the average KAR-smoothing mean error by considering only a subset of the IC with a given upper limit on σ_{SM} . Results are summarised in Table 2, where the numbers N are taken from a study by Høg (1982 Sept 19). If we look at the average mean errors defined as $(\bar{p}_{\text{KAR}}^*)^{\frac{1}{2}}$, we find that the 5000 FK5 stars contribute more to the AR than all the other programme stars! This is rather misleading, however, since the long intervals $T = 500 \text{ s}$ would mean that the variance goes up by a large factor between transits. (Using the geometric mean of p_{min}^* , p_{max}^* is also deceptive when there is a large factor

between them.) A more correct picture results from taking $(\bar{p}_{\max}^*)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ as a measure of the typical AR mean error (last column in Table 2). A numerical simulation of KAR-smoothing with a realistic (or, even better, a real) star distribution with respect to transit times and σ_{SM} is clearly desirable. It appears however that there is some hope of achieving 0.2 as in the OGAR with only IC positions.

Table 2. Number of stars (N) in the IC at various accuracy levels (σ_{SM}), the mean time (T) between transits for a 20 am slit group, and the estimated mean errors of KAR-smoothing

σ_{SM}	N	T	$(\bar{p}_{KAR}^*)^{\frac{1}{2}}$	$(\bar{p}_{\max}^*)^{\frac{1}{2}}$
≤ 0.10 as	5,000	500 s	≤ 0.19 as	≤ 0.36 as
≤ 0.25	25,000	100	≤ 0.20	≤ 0.22
≤ 1.0	56,000	43	≤ 0.32	≤ 0.32
≤ 1.5	90,000 (B < 11)	28	≤ 0.35	≤ 0.35

The calculations above essentially refer to the transverse attitude (σ_{ϕ} and σ_{θ}). For the longitudinal attitude (σ_{ψ}), about the z axis, T in Table 2 should be divided by 4 if the SM includes 40 am vertical slits. This would give $(\bar{p}_{\max}^*)^{\frac{1}{2}} \leq 0.15$ as, which is only marginally acceptable in view of slit inconsistencies (Petersen, 1982 Nov 16). By using also IDT data in the AR (Lindgren, 1982 Sept 24 = NDAC/LO/006) we can certainly do much better about the z axis. If the IDT observations are formally treated as a gyro signal, we can estimate the improved r as follows. Among the four stars typically inside the FOV, there is almost certainly one brighter than $B = 9$. During its passage across the FOV, which takes 18 s, it is observed in 8 frames with average $\sigma_{\eta} \sim 10$ mas per frame. Therefore, the average spin rate during this 18 s interval can be obtained with mean error ~ 1 mas/s. Thus $r^2 \sim (1 \text{ mas/s})^2 (18 \text{ s}) \sim 2 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ as}^2/\text{s}$. Combining with $\sigma_{SM} \leq 0.25$ as and $T = 25$ s from Table 2 (vertical SM slits) we get $(\bar{p}_{\max}^*)^{\frac{1}{2}} \leq 0.06$ as.

5.2. Dynamic reconstitution

In order to restrict the number of free parameters, we shall in the following always consider the "nominal OGAR" situation with

$$r^2 = 0.001 \text{ as}^2/\text{s}, \quad \sigma_{SM} = 0.08 \text{ as}, \quad T = 43 \text{ s} \quad (60)$$

and only make different assumptions concerning the torque noise PSD. Recall that the smoothed KAR gives in this case the average mean error 0.091 as, eqn (59).

Table 3 gives some estimates for the unpredictable torques. The third column gives the rms amplitude of the full torque; the next column, predictability, indicates what fraction of the full amplitude can perhaps be predicted after some in-orbit calibration. The residual power is computed as $[\text{rms ampl.} \times (1 - \text{predictability})]^2$. The last column gives the jitter amplitude computed as $[\text{rms ampl.} \times (1 - \text{predictability})]/[J(2\pi f)^2]$, with $J = 385 \text{ kg m}^2$.

Table 3. Magnitude estimate of torque noise power

Source	f	rms amplitude	predictability	residual power	jitter amplitude
nututation	2.10^{-5} Hz	2.10^{-7} Nm	0.9	$4.10^{-16} \text{ N}^2\text{m}^2$	600"
gyroscope	1.10^{-4}	1.10^{-5}	0.99	1.10^{-14}	100"
radiation pressure (3Ω)	4.10^{-4}	2.10^{-6}	0.95	1.10^{-14}	10"
- " - (6Ω)	8.10^{-4}	4.10^{-7}	0.9	2.10^{-15}	1"
- " - ($> 6\Omega$)	$10^{-3} - 10^{-2}$	1.10^{-7} ?	0	1.10^{-14}	0".3
flexible modes	4	1.10^{-3}	0	1.10^{-6}	0".001

Apart from high-frequency vibrations induced by the thrusters, the residual torques are of the order of 10^{-7} Nm. These cannot cause jitter with amplitude over 0.01 as, unless their frequency is less than 0.01 Hz. The total power below 0.01 Hz is $3.10^{-14} \text{ N}^2\text{m}^2$, corresponding to an average PSD $P_e(f) \approx 3.10^{-12} \text{ N}^2\text{m}^2/\text{Hz}$ at $f < 0.01$ Hz. However the average density below

0.001 Hz is rather higher, about $2 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ N}_m^2/\text{Hz}$.

Case 1: White noise spectrum

If we assume a constant $P_e = 2v^2 = 10^{-11} \text{ N}_m^2/\text{Hz}$, we get

$$v/J = 5.8 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ rad s}^{-1.5} = 1.2 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ as s}^{-1.5} \quad (61)$$

Eqn (52) yields $\xi = 3.2$, indicating that DAR is just marginally useful (Table 1). With the analytical method of Section 4.2 we get

$$(\bar{p}_{\text{DAR}}^*)^{\frac{1}{2}} = 0.889 \quad (\bar{p}_{\text{KAR}}^*) = 0.081 \text{ as} \quad (62)$$

Table 4 gives the average smoothed mean error $(\bar{p}_{\text{DAR}}^*)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ as function of the torque noise level P_e , computed by means of the numerical method of Section 4.1 and also with the analytical approximation of Section 4.2.

Table 4. Average smoothed mean error $(\bar{p}_{\text{DAR}}^*)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ versus torque noise level P_e

P_e [N_m^2/Hz]	10^{-16}	10^{-15}	10^{-14}	10^{-13}	10^{-12}	10^{-11}	10^{-10}	10^{-9}	∞
m.e. [mas] numerical	22.9	30.5	40.6	53.8	69.9	83.8	89.2	90.5	-
m.e. [mas] analytical	22.9	30.4	40.4	53.0	67.6	80.9	88.4	90.6	91.1

Case 2: Markov spectrum

With $P_e(f) = 10^{-11} \text{ N}_m^2/\text{Hz}$ at low frequencies ($f < f_0$) and varying the cut-off frequency f_0 , we obtain the average smoothed mean errors in Table 5. It is seen that the m.e. is most sensitive to f_0 in the range 0.1-1 mHz. For lower frequencies the equivalent white-noise PSD (i.e. the value P_e which according to Table 4 allows the same DAR accuracy as the Markov spectrum) is of the order of the Markov PSD at $f \sim 0.1-1$ mHz, again indicating this to be the critical frequency range. A few experiments with damped-oscillator spectra (Case 3) support this conclusion but are otherwise unremarkable.

Table 5. Average smoothed mean error $(\bar{p}_{\text{DAR}}^*)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ versus cut-off frequency f_o , for a Markov torque noise spectrum with $P_e(0) = 10^{-11} N_m^2/\text{Hz}$

f_o [Hz]	10^{-6}	10^{-5}	10^{-4}	10^{-3}	10^{-2}	10^{-1}	∞
m.e. [mas] numerical	25.8	37.8	54.6	73.5	82.8:	84:	83.8*
lg(equiv. white PSD)	-15.6	-14.2	-12.9	-11.8	-11.1	-11.0	-11.0

* from Table 4

6. Interpretation in terms of three-axes attitude

6.1. Requirements

Requirements on the on-ground AR are best formulated in terms of the attitude errors ϕ , θ , ψ about the three telescope axes $\underline{x}$, $\underline{y}$, $\underline{z}$, respectively. With

$$\underline{\varepsilon} := \phi \underline{x} + \theta \underline{y} + \psi \underline{z} \quad (63)$$

denoting the total attitude error, we may separate the pointing error

$$\underline{\Delta z} := \underline{\varepsilon} \wedge \underline{z} = \theta \underline{x} - \phi \underline{y} \quad (64)$$

from the spin error

$$\underline{z}' \underline{\varepsilon} = \psi \quad (65)$$

In the fundamental observation equation (A.5.8)

$$\Delta \eta = \sec \zeta \underline{s}' \underline{\Delta u} - \underline{z}' \underline{\varepsilon} - \tan \zeta \underline{s}' \underline{\Delta z} \mp \frac{1}{2} \Delta \gamma \quad (66)$$

where $\underline{u}$ is the unit vector towards the object and $\underline{s} := \sec \zeta \underline{z} \wedge \underline{u}$, the spin error is exactly the same for all stars in a frame, and is eliminated in the set solution, while the pointing error enters with different (but numerically small) factors for the different stars, thus adding noise to the measurements. For a star in the p-field we have

$$\underline{u} \simeq \underline{p} = \cos(\frac{1}{2}\gamma) \underline{x} + \sin(\frac{1}{2}\gamma) \underline{y} \quad (67)$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned}\underline{s}'\underline{\Delta z} &\approx (\underline{z}'\underline{\wedge p})'(\underline{\varepsilon}'\underline{\wedge z}) = (\underline{z}'\underline{\varepsilon})(\underline{p}'\underline{z}) - (\underline{z}'\underline{z})(\underline{p}'\underline{\varepsilon}) = -\underline{p}'\underline{\varepsilon} \\ &= -\phi \cos(\frac{1}{2}\gamma) - \theta \sin(\frac{1}{2}\gamma)\end{aligned}\quad (68)$$

and similarly for a star in the f-field,

$$\underline{s}'\underline{\Delta z} \approx -\underline{f}'\underline{\varepsilon} = -\phi \cos(\frac{1}{2}\gamma) + \theta \sin(\frac{1}{2}\gamma)\quad (69)$$

The rms value of the pointing-error term $-\tan \zeta \underline{s}'\underline{\Delta z}$ is consequently

$$\begin{aligned}\delta\eta_{\text{rms}} &\approx 12^{-\frac{1}{2}} \phi_t \left[\cos^2(\frac{1}{2}\gamma) \sigma_\phi^2 \pm 2\cos(\frac{1}{2}\gamma)\sin(\frac{1}{2}\gamma) \rho_{\phi\theta} \sigma_\phi \sigma_\theta + \sin^2(\frac{1}{2}\gamma) \sigma_\theta^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\approx 12^{-\frac{1}{2}} \phi_t \left[\cos^2(\frac{1}{2}\gamma) \sigma_\phi^2 + \sin^2(\frac{1}{2}\gamma) \sigma_\theta^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}\end{aligned}\quad (70)$$

where $\phi_t = 0.0157$ rad is the transverse FOV and a possible correlation between ϕ and θ is eliminated by taking the mean of the two field directions.

As shown by Høgl (1982 Aug 8), the measurement noise contributed by the pointing-error term in (66) propagates to the abscissa determinations, where the degradation factor is

$$F := \frac{\sigma_{\text{absc}}(\sigma_\phi, \sigma_\theta)}{\sigma_{\text{absc}}(0, 0)} \approx \left[1 + n \delta\eta_{\text{rms}}^2 / \langle \sigma_\eta^2 \rangle \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}\quad (71)$$

Here, $n = \phi_\ell / (T_4 v) \approx 8.4$ is the number of frames per passage across the longitudinal FOV (ϕ_ℓ) and $\langle \sigma_\eta^2 \rangle^{\frac{1}{2}} \approx 0.010$ as is the average photon-statistical mean error per frame. With the indicated values and $\gamma = 58^\circ$,

$$F \approx 1 + 0.9 \left[0.765 \sigma_\phi^2 + 0.235 \sigma_\theta^2 \right]\quad (72)$$

($\sigma_\phi, \sigma_\theta$ in as). For negligible impact on the overall accuracy, $\sigma_\phi, \sigma_\theta \lesssim 0.1 - 0.2$ as is implied.

The spin-error requirement,

$$\sigma_\psi \lesssim 0.15 \text{ as}\quad (73)$$

follows from the resolution of slit inconsistencies in the set solution (Petersen, 1982 Nov 16).

6.2. Translation from single-axis to full attitude

For simplicity we assumed in Sections 2-5 that the axis $\underline{a}$ was parallel to one of the SM slit groups and that other parts of the SM could be neglected. In reality we are however interested in the attitude errors ϕ , θ , ψ about the three orthogonal telescope axes, which are in general not parallel to any slit group. Also, there may be up to six different slit groups contributing to the AR, so clearly at least some axis must get partial information from several slit groups. How then can we translate our results on a single axis to the full three-axes problem?

A simple solution is indicated by the fact that T and σ_{SM} , in the average variance formulae for both KAR and DAR, invariably occur in the combination $(T\sigma_{SM}^2)^p$ for some exponent p . This can be understood as a consequence of the steady-state Riccati equation (48), where these quantities enter only in the rate-of-weight matrix $\underline{S}$, eqn (49). This suggests that an equivalent rate-of-weight figure $(T\sigma_{SM}^2)^{-1}$ can be computed for any particular axis by conventional least-squares combination of the various transits at different slit groups occurring in a given time interval.

With the full attitude error $\underline{\epsilon}$ according to (63), a transit across a SM slit group along axis $\underline{a}$ gives an observation equation with LHS $\underline{a}'\underline{\epsilon}$ and mean error σ (say). With the SM configuration in Fig. 4 we have, on the average, one transit on each of the 20 am segments numbered 1 to 8 per time interval of length T (= 43 s in the nominal case). The corresponding axes are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \underline{a}_1 &= \sin(\frac{1}{2}\gamma)\sin(i)\underline{x} - \cos(\frac{1}{2}\gamma)\sin(i)\underline{y} + \cos(i)\underline{z} \\ \underline{a}_2 &= \underline{z} \\ \dots \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (74)$$

where $i = 45^\circ$. Forming the eight observation equations and inverting the normal equations matrix we get $\text{diag}[4\sin^2(\frac{1}{2}\gamma)\sin^2 i \quad 4\cos^2(\frac{1}{2}\gamma)\sin^2 i \quad 4+4\cos^2 i]$. Thus, the equivalent transit errors per axis and T -interval are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_{SM\phi} &= [2\sin(\frac{1}{2}\gamma)\sin(i)]^{-1} \sigma \simeq 1.46 \sigma \\ \sigma_{SM\theta} &= [2\cos(\frac{1}{2}\gamma)\sin(i)]^{-1} \sigma \simeq 0.81 \sigma \\ \sigma_{SM\psi} &= [2(1 + \cos^2 i)^{\frac{1}{2}}]^{-1} \sigma \simeq 0.41 \sigma \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (\text{uncorrelated transits}) \quad (75)$$

It is worth noting that the errors in ϕ , θ , ψ are on the average uncorrelated, and that the vertical segments (2, 4, 6, 8) consequently contribute only to the determination of ψ . If we delete the observation equations for the vertical slit segments, we get $\sigma_{SM\psi} = (2 \cos i)^{-1} \sigma \simeq 0.71 \sigma$, while $\sigma_{SM\phi}$ and $\sigma_{SM\theta}$ are unaltered.

Eqn (75) applies only if the observations are uncorrelated, as can be assumed if photon noise dominates. For the real-time AR, and also for the on-ground AR with inaccurate star positions, the catalogue errors dominate for most stars. These give of course strongly correlated errors when the same star is being observed at different slit groups. Consider for instance a star with catalogue position errors $\Delta\eta$, $\Delta\zeta$ crossing the two segments 1 and 2 in Fig. 4. The corresponding transit error (normal to the slits) at segment 1 is $e_1 = \Delta\eta \cos i + \Delta\zeta \sin i$, while at segment 2 it is $e_2 = \Delta\eta$. The correlation coefficient is $\cos i$, if we assume that $\Delta\eta$ and $\Delta\zeta$ are uncorrelated and have the same mean error (σ). The two observation equations are orthogonalized through pre-multiplying by

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & \cos i \\ \cos i & 1 \end{pmatrix}^{-\frac{1}{2}} = \begin{pmatrix} \operatorname{cosec} i & -\cot i \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (76)$$

Performing this on each pair of observations, 1-2, 3-4, 5-6, 7-8, we get the modified inverse normal equations matrix $\operatorname{diag}[4\sin^2(\frac{1}{2}\gamma) \quad 4\cos^2(\frac{1}{2}\gamma) \quad 4]$.

Thus,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_{SM\phi} &= [2\sin(\frac{1}{2}\gamma)]^{-1} \sigma \simeq 1.03 \sigma \\ \sigma_{SM\theta} &= [2\cos(\frac{1}{2}\gamma)]^{-1} \sigma \simeq 0.57 \sigma \\ \sigma_{SM\psi} &= \frac{1}{2} \sigma \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (\text{correlated transits}) \quad (77)$$

If there are no vertical segments, the original observation equations are still uncorrelated when catalogue errors dominate, and we get $\sigma_{SM\phi} = 1.46 \sigma$, $\sigma_{SM\theta} = 0.81 \sigma$, $\sigma_{SM\psi} = 0.71 \sigma$, i.e. a factor $\sqrt{2}$ worse. Clearly, vertical slits are very useful for the real-time AR and for the a posteriori AR using IC star positions.

Consider now the nominal OGAR case (60), where $\sigma_{SM} = 0.08$ as is interpreted as the mean error per transit, i.e. σ in (75). Thus $\sigma_{SM\phi} = 0.117$ as, $\sigma_{SM\theta} = 0.065$ as, and $\sigma_{SM\psi} = 0.033$ as. Inserting in (14) we get for the KAR

$\sigma_\phi = 0.11$ as, $\sigma_\theta = 0.08$ as, and $\sigma_\psi = 0.06$ as. If however we take only the 25,000 stars with positions better than 0.25 as, putting $T = 100$ s and $\sigma = 0.25$ as in (77), we get $\sigma_\phi = 0.20$ as, $\sigma_\theta = 0.15$ as, and $\sigma_\psi = 0.14$ as.

7. Conclusions

Concerning the main issue of this note, the accuracy of DAR as compared to KAR, we conclude that dynamic modelling will be useful only if residual (unpredictable) torques are on a level $P_e < 10^{-11} \text{ N}^2\text{m}^2/\text{Hz}$ in the frequency range 0.1 - 1 mHz. Since present torque estimates (Table 3) are precisely at this limit, it is far from certain that DAR is worthwhile.

On the other hand it appears that simple KAR-smoothing is fully sufficient in view of the requirements in Section 6.1. It may even be sufficient to use IC positions, successively updated by means of AR residuals, without iterating the AR for the first part of the mission. In any case the accuracy about the $\underline{z}$ axis (σ_ψ) required for resolving slit inconsistencies in the set solutions can certainly be reached by using IDT data in the AR.

FIGURE 4. Definition of SM segments 1 to 8.

APPENDICES

For the reader's convenience and future reference, we give here some definitions and elementary results from the theory of stochastic processes and optimal linear filtering.

I. Properties of certain stochastic processes

A stochastic process (random function) is a function $x(t)$ whose values are random variables. In general, a stochastic process is specified by the joint probability distribution functions

$$F_{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \Pr\{x(t_1) < x_1, x(t_2) < x_2, \dots, x(t_n) < x_n\} \quad (\text{I.1})$$

for any set of arguments $\{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n\}$ and any $n \geq 1$. If we restrict ourselves to normal (gaussian) processes, for which (I.1) is an n -dimensional normal probability distribution function, it is however sufficient to specify the distribution functions for $n = 1$ and 2 ; the higher-order distributions are computable in terms of these. Moreover, the first- and second-order distributions are completely specified by the first two moments

$$m(t) := E[x(t)] \quad (\text{I.2})$$

$$B(t, s) := E[x(t)x(s)] \quad (\text{I.3})$$

For our purposes $x(t)$ can always be treated as normal, in which case $m(t)$ and $B(t, s)$ provide a complete description of the process. — We also define the centered second moment,

$$C(t, s) := E\{[x(t) - m(t)]\{x(s) - m(s)\}\} = B(t, s) - m(t)m(s) \quad (\text{I.4})$$

The process $x(t)$ is said to be stationary if $m(t)$ is independent of t and $B(t, s)$ depends only on $t-s$. We then define

$$m_x := E[x(t)] \quad (\text{mean}) \quad (\text{I.5})$$

$$B_x(\tau) := E[x(t)x(t+\tau)] \quad (\text{autocorrelation}) \quad (\text{I.6})$$

$$C_x(\tau) := E\{[x(t) - m_x]\{x(t+\tau) - m_x\}\} = B_x(\tau) - m_x^2 \quad (\text{autocovariance}) \quad (\text{I.7})$$

The power spectral density (PSD) of the stationary process $x(t)$ is

$$P_x(f) := 4 \int_0^{\infty} C_x(\tau) \cos(2\pi f\tau) d\tau \quad (f \geq 0) \quad (\text{I.8})$$

and from the Fourier Theorem we also have

$$C_x(\tau) = \int_0^{\infty} P_x(f) \cos(2\pi f\tau) df \quad (\text{I.9})$$

In particular, the variance of the process is

$$C_x(0) = \int_0^{\infty} P_x(f) df \quad (\text{I.10})$$

If $C_x(\tau)$ has a continuous second derivative, then $\dot{x}(t) := dx/dt$ is also a stationary process with

$$m_{\dot{x}} = 0 \quad (\text{I.11})$$

$$C_{\dot{x}}(\tau) = -\frac{d^2}{d\tau^2} C_x(\tau) \quad (\text{I.12})$$

$$P_{\dot{x}}(f) = (2\pi f)^2 P_x(f) \quad (\text{I.13})$$

More generally, the PSD of the process

$$y(t) := a_n \frac{d^n x}{dt^n} + a_{n-1} \frac{d^{n-1} x}{dt^{n-1}} + \dots + a_1 \frac{dx}{dt} + a_0 x \quad (\text{I.14})$$

(if it exists) is

$$P_y(f) = |a_n (j2\pi f)^n + a_{n-1} (j2\pi f)^{n-1} + \dots + a_1 j2\pi f + a_0|^2 P_x(f) \quad (\text{I.15})$$

with $j := \sqrt{-1}$.

The Wiener process

The Wiener process $w(t)$ is a non-stationary, normal stochastic process with the following properties:

$$E[w(t)] = 0 \quad (\text{I.16})$$

$$E[\{w(t) - w(s)\}^2] = |t - s| \quad (\text{I.17})$$

$$E[\{w(t_1) - w(s_1)\}\{w(t_2) - w(s_2)\}] = 0, \quad [t_1, s_1] \cap [t_2, s_2] = \emptyset \quad (\text{I.18})$$

Eqn (I.17) means that $w(t)$ has unit incremental variance, while (I.18) says that it has independent increments in non-overlapping intervals. The process with unit incremental variance may be called a unit Wiener process, since the scaled process $cw(t)$ (with incremental variance $= c^2 dt$) is often also called a Wiener process.

Unit white noise

Although $w(t)$ is not differentiable, the stationary process formally identified as $\dot{w}(t)$ is an extremely useful concept. It can be seen as the limit of

$$n_h(t) := h^{-1}[w(t+h) - w(t)], \quad h > 0 \quad (\text{I.19})$$

as $h \rightarrow 0$. From the properties of $w(t)$ we find that

$$m_{n_h} = 0 \quad (\text{I.20})$$

$$C_{n_h}(\tau) = \begin{cases} (h - |\tau|)/h^2, & |\tau| \leq h; \\ 0, & |\tau| > h \end{cases} \quad (\text{I.21})$$

$$P_{n_h}(f) = 2\text{sinc}^2(\pi hf) \quad (\text{I.22})$$

Thus, for $h = 0$ we obtain the unit white noise process $n(t) = \dot{w}(t)$ with

$$m_n = 0 \quad (\text{I.23})$$

$$C_n(\tau) = \delta(\tau) \quad (\text{I.24})$$

$$P_n(f) = 2 \quad (\text{I.25})$$

Processes with rational PSD

A stochastic process $y(t)$ with rational power spectral density

$$P_y(f) = 2 \frac{|b_m(j\omega)^m + b_{m-1}(j\omega)^{m-1} + \dots + b_1j\omega + b_0|^2}{|(j\omega)^k + a_{k-1}(j\omega)^{k-1} + \dots + a_1j\omega + a_0|^2} \quad (\text{I.26})$$

($\omega := 2\pi f$), $m < k$, may be generated by means of an n :th order differential equation driven by unit white noise:

$$y(t) = b_m \frac{d^m x}{dt^m} + \dots + b_1 \frac{dx}{dt} + b_0 x \quad (\text{I.27})$$

$$\frac{d^k x}{dt^k} + a_{k-1} \frac{d^{k-1} x}{dt^{k-1}} + \dots + a_1 \frac{dx}{dt} + a_0 x = n(t) \quad (\text{I.28})$$

Introducing the k -vectors

$$\underline{x} := \left(x \quad \dot{x} \quad \ddot{x} \quad \dots \quad \frac{d^{k-1} x}{dt^{k-1}} \right)' \quad (\text{I.29})$$

$$\underline{w} := \left(w_1 \quad w_2 \quad \dots \quad w_k \right)' \quad (\text{I.30})$$

where w_i are independent unit Wiener processes, and the (k,k) -matrices

$$\underline{\Phi} := \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 & 0 \\ -a_0 & -a_1 & -a_2 & \dots & -a_{k-2} & -a_{k-1} \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{I.31})$$

$$\underline{\Gamma} := \text{diag}(0 \quad 0 \quad \dots \quad 1) \quad (\text{I.32})$$

eqn (I.28) transforms into a system of k first-order differential equations

$$d\underline{x} = \underline{\Phi} \underline{x} dt + \underline{\Gamma} d\underline{w} \quad (\text{I.33})$$

Also

$$y(t) = \underline{b}' \underline{x} \quad (\text{I.34})$$

where $\underline{b}$ is the k -vector containing the $m+1$ elements b_i augmented by zeroes. Eqns (I.33) - (I.34) provide a dynamical model for a fairly wide class of normal stochastic processes.

II. Optimal continuous filtering

Let $\underline{s}(t)$ be an n -dimensional state vector describing a time-invariant, linear dynamical system through the differential equation

$$d\underline{s} = \underline{F}\underline{s} dt + \underline{G}d\underline{w} \quad (\text{II.1})$$

where $\underline{F}$, $\underline{G}$ are given (n,n) -matrices and $\underline{w}(t)$ is an n -vector of independent unit Wiener processes. The system is measured in the form of linear differential observation equations of order m (= number of observables):

$$d\underline{y} = \underline{A}\underline{s} dt + \underline{R}d\underline{w} \quad (\text{II.2})$$

where the dimensions are $\underline{y}(m)$, $\underline{A}(m,n)$, $\underline{R}(m,m)$, and $\underline{w}(m)$. The unit Wiener process vector $\underline{w}$ represents measurement noise and is of course independent of the process noise vector $\underline{w}$.

A filtered estimate $\hat{\underline{s}}(t)$ is based on observations up to and including time t , i.e. on $\underline{y}(s)$ for $s \leq t$. We may assume that, at some initial time t_0 , the state estimate $\hat{\underline{s}}(t_0)$ is given with covariance $\underline{P}(t_0)$. The well-known Kalman-Bucy filter provides the optimum filtered estimate at $t \geq t_0$ through the differential equation

$$d\hat{\underline{s}} = \underline{F}\hat{\underline{s}} dt + \underline{K}(t)[d\underline{y}(t) - \underline{A}\hat{\underline{s}} dt] \quad (\text{II.3})$$

where $\underline{K}(t)$, the Kalman gain matrix, depends on the current filter covariance:

$$\underline{K}(t) = \underline{P}(t) \underline{A}' (\underline{R}\underline{R}')^{-1} \quad (\text{II.4})$$

This gives the optimum weight to the observed change of state compared to that predicted from the process equation (II.1).

The covariance of $\hat{\underline{s}}(t)$ develops according to the Riccati equation

$$\dot{\underline{P}} = \underline{F}\underline{P} + \underline{P}\underline{F}' + \underline{G}\underline{G}' - \underline{P}\underline{A}'(\underline{R}\underline{R}')^{-1}\underline{A}\underline{P} \quad (\text{II.5})$$

from the initial covariance $\underline{P}(t_0)$. The solution $\underline{P}(t)$, $t \geq t_0$, can be obtained in closed form for the time invariant process-measurement system (when $\underline{F}$, $\underline{G}$, $\underline{A}$, and $\underline{R}$ are fixed matrices) as follows. Set up the Hamiltonian matrix

$$\underline{H} = \begin{pmatrix} -\underline{F}' & \underline{A}'(\underline{R}\underline{R}')^{-1}\underline{A} \\ \underline{G}\underline{G}' & \underline{F} \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{II.6})$$

of dimension $(2n, 2n)$ and solve

$$\frac{d}{dt} \underline{L}(t) = \underline{H}\underline{L}(t), \quad \underline{L}(t_0) = \underline{I}_{2n} \quad (\text{II.7})$$

In the time-invariant case this gives

$$\underline{L}(t) = \exp[(t-t_0)\underline{H}] = \underline{I} + (t-t_0)\underline{H} + \frac{1}{2}(t-t_0)^2 \underline{H}\underline{H} + \dots \quad (\text{II.8})$$

Then partition $\underline{L}(t)$ into four (n, n) -matrices:

$$\underline{L} = \begin{pmatrix} \underline{L}_{11} & \underline{L}_{12} \\ \underline{L}_{21} & \underline{L}_{22} \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{II.9})$$

Finally,

$$\underline{P}(t) = \left[\underline{L}_{21}(t) + \underline{L}_{22}(t)\underline{P}(t_0) \right] \left[\underline{L}_{11}(t) + \underline{L}_{12}(t)\underline{P}(t_0) \right]^{-1} \quad (\text{II.10})$$

It is sometimes required to obtain the stationary solution to the Riccati equation, i.e. for $\dot{\underline{P}} = \underline{0}$ in (II.5). This can also be obtained via the Hamiltonian (II.6). If $\underline{h}_1, \underline{h}_2, \dots, \underline{h}_n$ are eigenvectors of $\underline{H}$ belonging to eigenvalues with positive real parts, we form the two (n, n) -matrices $\underline{D}_1, \underline{D}_2$ from

$$\begin{pmatrix} \underline{h}_1 & \underline{h}_2 & \dots & \underline{h}_n \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \underline{D}_1 \\ \underline{D}_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{II.11})$$

and obtain the stationary covariance as

$$\underline{P} = \underline{D}_2 \underline{D}_1^{-1} \quad (\text{II.12})$$